

ISSN 2181-8622

Manufacturing technology problems

**Scientific and Technical Journal
Namangan Institute of
Engineering and Technology**

**Volume 8
Issue 1
2023**

Publishing office of «Vela Verlag Waldkraiburg», Munich. Germany. December. 18–19. 2012. P. 222–225.

12. Siddikov I.K., Sattarov Kh.A., Khujamatov Kh.E., Dekhkonov O.R. Agzamova M. Modeling of Magnetic Circuits of Electromagnetic Transducers of the Three-phases Current //2018 14th International Scientific - Technical Conference On Actual Problems of Electronic Instrument Engineering (Apeie) Proceedings. In 8 Volume Part 5 Novosibirsk 2018;

13. Сиддиков И.Х., Аъзамов С.С., Тожибоев Ж.Б. Возобновляемый источник энергии систем электроснабжения истраченной реактивной мощностью и управление элементарным улучшением / Siddikov I.H.,

14. Azamov S.S., Tozhiboev Zh.B. Renewable energy source of power supply systems with expired reactive power and management of elementary improvement Просвещение и познание 2022. № 9 (16) научно-методический журнал ст-3-10.

15. Modelling of the asymmetrical quantities of asynchronous motors reactive powers supply on the basis of current transducers Siddikov Ilkhomjon Hakimovich, Boikhanov Zailobiddin Urazalai o'g'li, A'zamov Saidikrom Saidmurodovich// Andijon mashinasozlik instituti mashinasozlik ilmiy-texnika jurnali varoq-143-152.

16. Rustam Baratov 1 , Nurali Pirmatov2 , Abdullo Panoev3 , Yakubjon Chulliyev1 , Sodiq Ruziyev1 and Almardon Mustafoqulov1 Achievement of electric energy savings through controlling frequency convertor in the operation process of asynchronous motors in textile enterprises// This content was downloaded from IP address 213.230.96.54 on 29/03/2023 at 08:14

17. A M Safarov¹, Kh A Sattarov², A M Mustafoqulov³ and Yu Yu Shoyimov⁴ Experimental research of magnetic circuits of current converters taking into account the nonlinearity of magnetic characteristics// A M Safarov *et al* 2022 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2176** 012006

18. D D Karimjonov, I X Siddikov, S S Azamov, and R Uzakov, Study on determination of an asynchronous motor's reactive power by the current-to-voltage converter. IP address 213.230.96.54 on 23/03/2023 at 07:07

19. Сиддиков И.Х., Махсудов М.Т., Боихонов З.У.. Асинхрон моторнинг реактив кувват истеъмолини назорат ва бошқариш тизими ток ўзгарткичлари // «Илм–фан, таълим ва ишлаб чиқаришнинг инновацион ривожлантиришдаги замонавий муаммолар» мавзусида ҳалқаро илмий–амалий конференция, Андижон 13 – 15 май 2020 йил, 481 – 485 бетлар.

20. “Qisqacha politexnik lug‘at”. O‘zbekiston ensiklopediyasi bosh tahririyati. T. Fan. 1992 y. 137-142с

21. Siddikov I.X., Anarboev M.A., Mirzaev N.N., Mamatqulov A.N., Statik va dinamik reaktiv quvvat manbalarini boshkaruv elementlari // Energiya va resurs tejash muammolari // Ilmiy jurnal (maxsus nashr) Toshkent 2013 № 3–4 39-42 б.

EVALUATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF DIAGNOSTICS OF THE CRANKSHAFT OF DIESEL LOCOMOTIVES

KUDRATOV SHOHJAKHON

Doctoral student of Tashkent State Transport University
E-mail: kudratov.shohjaxon@bk.ru, phone: (+99890) 788-85-83

Abstract. A significant increase in the efficiency of the equipment used is achieved through the introduction of modern methods and means of technical diagnostics. Technical diagnostics makes it

possible to increase the overhaul life of units and assemblies, prevent the dismantling and disassembly of units and individual mechanisms, reduce downtime for technical reasons, reduce the labor intensity of maintenance and operating costs, which significantly increases the efficiency of the use of equipment. Technical diagnostics makes it possible to control the technical condition of machines during operation and predict their service life until the next repair in accordance with the indicators obtained. It allows not only to assess the technical condition of the units and assemblies of machines, but also makes it possible to determine the volumes and types of necessary work using in-place methods. The main tasks of technical diagnostics are: control of the technical condition for compliance with the requirements of technical documentation; search for the causes of failure (malfunction); collection of initial data for forecasting the technical condition; maintaining machine reliability.

Keywords: diesel, crankshaft, diagnostics, operation, overhaul, lubrication, cleanliness.

Introduction. To maintain locomotives in working condition, to prevent gradual failures due to aging and wear of equipment, a smoothly preventive system of repairs is needed. It includes a set of interrelated provisions and standards that determine the organization and procedure for the maintenance and repair of rolling stock. The advantage of this system is the ability to guarantee the established resource and safe operation of the most important units and parts of the diesel locomotive.

The main disadvantage of the system is the high level of costs for the production of a specified amount of work for a given type of maintenance or repair. However, despite the large material costs, the use of a preventive system is advisable to ensure a high level of safety and guarantee reliability in terms of serviceability for a strictly defined period of operation of the locomotive fleet.

Research method. An example of a research method is the malfunctions that occur during operation. When overhauling the engine, especially after grinding the crankshaft, many do not attach importance to the cleanliness of the crankshaft oil channels, clean them correctly. This operation is also very important because when grinding the crankshaft to the repair size of the liners, abrasive and processing products (metal dust) get into the oil channels. If after that you do not thoroughly rinse the oil channels of the crankshaft, then at the first start of the engine, the remaining dirt can do a lot of trouble, at best, it will simply greatly reduce the life of the engine. Therefore, thorough flushing of

the internal cavities of the crankshaft is very important. The crankshaft oil channels, in addition to their function of supplying oil to friction pairs (crankshaft journals and liners), also serve to trap dirt particles (in special cavities) that can pass through the filter (very small particles) using centrifugal force. There were times when dirt completely clogged the oil channels, and from this, naturally, friction pairs began to work dry and quickly failed.

Oil starvation of the engine leads to irreversible consequences - in addition to penny liners, the crankshaft is damaged. And it often happens that the seizures on the crankshaft remain larger than the last repair size, and this is the purchase of a new expensive part. Oil starvation of the engine does not mean that there is no oil at all, it just wasn't enough for some parts due to the low level, low throughput of the lubrication system due to clogging or other reasons. Not necessarily the entire engine does not receive oil - most often there is not enough oil in individual engine components.

Consequences of engine oil starvation. For example, when the crankshaft rotates, it does not come into contact with the liners, there is always oil between them, the so-called oil wedge. But when there is not enough oil, it stops flowing to the crankshaft and liners, then this oil wedge disappears and the shaft begins to rub against the liners and the shaft wedges due to friction and the resulting temperature increase, but since it continues to rotate by inertia, this wedge breaks, the more thereby tearing out the surface layer of metal from both surfaces. The result is an insert in foil, deep scuffs on

the crankshaft. If the oil pressure methodically gradually begins to decrease in the system, that is, it passes through the pipeline less, the connecting rod bearings of the crankshaft will suffer first of all, since they are located the farthest and the oil approaches them according to the residual principle. One of the most important elements of the internal combustion engine is the crankshaft. Due to it, energy from fuel combustion can be transferred to adjacent elements and ensure the rotation of the wheels. Responsible for reducing friction losses and preventing the wedge of parts at the point of contact of the crankshaft with the engine block bed (main bearings) and piston rods (rod bearings).

- **Indigenous.** Such liners are located between the shaft itself and the places where it passes through the engine housing;

- **Connecting rod.** They are installed between the connecting rods and the crankshaft journals.

Results. One of the important tasks is to improve the diagnostic method of the crankshaft. D49 diesels were used in diagnostics. A thermal sensor is installed on the connecting rod and root joints of the crankshaft. The oil has protection against this, but it does not signal a crankshaft failure. Thermosensor DS18B20 is used for this. Basic functional options DS18B20 is a temperature converter. The resolution of the temperature converter can be changed by the user and consists of 9, 10, 11, or 12 bits, corresponding to 0.5 °C, 0.25 °C, 0.125 °C, and 0.0625 °C, respectively.

Resolution is set to 12-bit by default. In the initial state, the DS18B20 is in a dormant state (in an inactive state). To start temperature measurement and conversion, the master must issue the start temperature conversion command [0x44]. After conversion, the received data is stored in a 2-byte register temperature in RAM, and the DS18B20 returns to the inactive state. If the DS18B20 is switched on with external power, the master can control the temperature conversion (after command [0x44]) according to the bus status. The DS18B20 will generate (response to the read time slot from the controller) logic "0" when a temperature conversion occurs. And a logical "1" when the conversion is done. If the DS18B20 is enabled with parasitic power, this notification technology cannot be used because the bus must be driven high (supply voltage) for the duration of the temperature conversion. In this case, the control device must independently control the conversion time. The DS18B20 temperature output is calibrated in degrees Celsius. The temperature data is stored as a 16-bit signed number. The flag (S) bits indicate whether the temperature is positive or negative: for positive numbers, S = 0, and for negative numbers, S = 1. If the DS18B20 is configured to convert 12-bit resolution, then all bits in the temperature register will contain valid data. For 11-bit resolution, bit 0 is undefined. For 10-bit resolution, bits 1 and 0 are undefined, and for 9-bit resolution 2, 1 and 0 are undefined.

Figure 1. DS18B20 Mounting Tool and Signal Processing via Microcontroller

Conclusion. The thermosensor DS18B20 is installed on the crankcase cover, as a result, it reports the temperature of the coolant coming out of the crankshaft. The signal from the sensor is sent to the microcontroller, as a result of which the signal is processed and displayed as a number. This makes it possible to diagnose the crankshaft of diesels. As a result, a diagnosis is made, the bearings are checked, the oil channels are inspected, or the high-pressure fuel pumps are inspected and their technical standards are checked. To extend the life of the crankshaft, change the oil in a timely manner, choose high-quality oil filters and change them at the same time as changing the oil. Periodically carry out a visual

inspection for diesel oil leakage, to prevent engine overheating. Monitor the condition of the cylinder cover to prevent water and fuel from getting into the diesel oil. DS18B20 it was found that the work on the creation of methods and means of technical diagnostics should be carried out in the direction of reducing labor intensity, improving the quality and efficiency of the obtained diagnostic information about the technical condition of the object being diagnosed. It is advisable to create diagnostic systems taking into account the modular basis, since it becomes possible to create additional functions and diagnostic capabilities by introducing an additional module into the system.

References

1. Khamidov, O.R., Grishchenko, A.V. Locomotive asynchronous traction motor rolling bearing fault detection based on current intelligent methods Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2021, 2131(4), 042084
2. Grishchenko, A.V., Kruchek, V.A., Kurilkin, D.N., Khamidov, O.R. Diagnostics of the Technical Condition of Rolling Bearings of Asynchronous Traction Motors of Locomotives Based on Data Mining Russian Electrical Engineering, 2020, 91(10), pp. 593–596
3. Valiev M. Sh. Application of a sensor to control the quality of the working process of a diesel locomotive / M. Sh. Valiev. - Locomotives. Gas motor fuel (Problems. Solutions. Prospects): Proceedings of the I International Scientific and Practical Conference. Samara, June 29, 2016 - 01 2017 - 2016. - p.69 - 73.
4. Valiev, M. Sh. Diagnostics of the working process of a diesel locomotive under operating conditions / M. Sh. Valiev. - Bulletin of Transport of the Volga Region. Samara State University of Communications. Samara - 2011. - No. 1 (25). – p.35 – 39. 317
5. Abyalimov, O., Petrochenko, S., Kodirov, N. Analyzing the Movement of a Freight Train at Stops on Flat Sections of the Railway Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, 2023, 510, pp. 165–171
6. Grachev, V. V. Assessment of the technical condition of diesel cylinders using an oxygen content sensor in exhaust gases / V. V. Grachev, M. Sh. Valiev // News of PGUPS

/ St. Petersburg State University of Railway Transport. - St. Petersburg. - 2011. - No. 2 (27). - With. 25 - 32.

7. Mamayev, S., Fayzibayev, S., Djanikulov, A., Kasimov, O. Method of Selection of Mainline Locomotives in the Unloaded State According to the Speed Characteristics Affecting the Electromechanical Vibrations of the WMB AIP Conference Proceedings, 2022, 2432, 030105

8. Valiev M.Sh., Kosimov Kh.R., Kudratov Sh.I. Evaluation of the technical condition of the diesel by working process parameters pp.312-317: In the collection: Technological support for the repair and improvement of the dynamic qualities of railway rolling stock. Materials of the V All-Russian scientific and technical conference with international participation. 2019. P. 312-317.

9. Valiev M.Sh. Diagnostics of crankcase oil flooding and protection of diesel engines from its impact in the collection: transport: science, education, production. collection of scientific papers. 2019. S. 253-256.

10. Valiev M.Sh. Evaluation of the technical condition of diesel cylinders using the sensor of the oxygen content in the exhaust gas In the collection: The future of mechanical engineering in Russia. Collection of reports of the Tenth All-Russian Conference of Young Scientists and Specialists (with international participation). 2017. S. 493-496.

11. Valiev M.Sh. Use of oxygen content sensor for control of excess air ratio of diesel Transsib News. 2017. No. 2 (30). pp. 9-17.

12. Valiev M.Sh. Use of a sensor for quality control of the diesel engine operation process Valiev M.Sh. In the collection: Locomotives. Gas fuel 2 (Problems. Solutions. Prospects). Materials of the I International Scientific and Practical Conference. 2016. S. 69-73.

13. Valiev M.Sh. Increasing the efficiency of diesel locomotives with the help of on-board diagnostics systems Valiev M.Sh. dissertation for the degree of candidate of technical sciences St. Petersburg State University of Communications. St. Petersburg, 2011

14. I.F.Pushkarev, E.A. Paxomov Control and assessment of the technical condition of diesel locomotives transport publishing house

15. Investigation of circular oscillations in the start mode of diesel locomotive UZTE16M. Dzhanikulov A.T., Valiev M.Sh. / News Transsib. 2021. No. 3 (47). P. 23-30.

16. Grachev VV, Bazilevskiy F.Yu., Valiev M.Sh. Device for control of excess air coefficient of diesel engine Proceedings of the Petersburg University of Communications. 2011. No. 3 (28). pp. 153-162.

17. Khamidov O., Kudratov Sh. Integral assessment of the technical condition of power plant systems of locomotives, International conference on "Language and cultures: Prospects for Development in the 21st Century" pp 165-168.

18. Khamidov O., Kudratov Sh. Evaluation of the thermal state of a cylinder – piston groups of diesel type D49, Academic research in modern science International scientific-online conference. pp 72-79.

19. Valiev M.Sh. Increasing the efficiency of on-board diagnostics systems on diesel locomotives abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of technical sciences St. Petersburg State University of Communications. St. Petersburg, 2011

20. Valiev M., Kosimov K. Diagnostics of the technical condition of the cylinder-piston group of diesel In the collection: E3S Web of Conferences. Sep. "International scientific conference "Construction mechanics, Hydraulics and Water resources engineering, CONMECHYHDRO 2021" 2021

C O N T E N T S

PRIMARY PROCESSING OF COTTON, TEXTILE AND LIGHT INDUSTRY

A.Shodmonkulov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev	
Analysis of load changes in the chain drive during the drying process of cotton falling from the longitudinal shelves of the drum.....	3
A.Xomidjonov	
Influence and characteristics of drying mechanisms in leather production on the derma layer.....	8
J.Monnopov, J.Kayumov, N.Maksudov	
Analysis of elastic fabrics for compression sportswear in the new assortment	13
S.Matismailov, K.Matmuratova, Sh.Korabayev, A.Yuldashev	
Investigation of the influence of speed modes of the combined drum on the quality indicators of the tape.....	18
A.Shodmonkulov, K.Jumaniyazov, R.Jamolov, X.Yuldashev	
Determination of the geometric and kinematic parameters of the developed chain gear for the 2SB-10 dryer.....	23
R.Jamolov, A.Shodmonkulov, X.Yuldashev	
Determination of dryer drum moisture extraction depending on its operating modes.....	27
A.Djuraev, K.Yuldashev, O.Teshaboyev	
Theoretical studies on screw conveyor for transportation and cleaning of linter and design of constructive parameters of transmissions.....	29
S.Khashimov, Kh.Isakhanov, R.Muradov	
Creation of technology and equipment for improved cleaning of cotton from small impurities.....	36
G.Juraeva, R.Muradov	
The process of technical grades of medium staple cotton at gin factories and its analysis.....	40
I.Xakimjonov	
Literature analysis on the research and development of the method of designing special clothes for workers of metal casting and metal processing enterprises.....	44
GROWING, STORAGE, PROCESSING AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS AND FOOD TECHNOLOGIES	
A.Khodjiev, A.Choriev, U.Raximov	
Improving the technology of production of functional nutrition juices.....	49
U.Nishonov	
Research in beverage technology intended to support the functions of the cardiovascular system.....	53

Z.Vokkosov, S.Hakimov	
Development of new types of vegetable juices and beverages technology...	59
CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGIES	
M.Latipova	
Analysis of the current status of thermoelectric materials and technology for obtaining and manufacturing half-elements.....	66
G.Ochilov, I.Boymatov, N.Ganiyeva	
Physico-chemical properties of activated adsorbents based on logan bentonite.....	72
U.Nigmatov	
Simulation of heat transfer process in absorber channels.....	77
T.Abduxakimov, D.Sherkuziev	
Procurement of local raw materials complex fertilizers with nitrogen-phosphate-potassium containing moisture.....	84
P.Tojiyev, X.Turaev, G.Nuraliyev, A.Djalilov	
Study of the structure and properties of polyvinyl chloride filled with bazalt mineral.....	89
M.Yusupov	
Investigation of phthalocyanine diamidophosphate- copper by thermal analysis.....	95
L.Oripova, P.Xayitov, A.Xudayberdiyev	
Testing new activated coals AU-T and AU-K from local raw materials when filtration of the waste mdea at gazlin gas processing plant.....	101
N.Kurbanov, D.Rozikova	
Based on energy efficient parameters of fruit drying chamber devices for small enterprises.....	107
Sh.Xakimov, M.Komoliddinov	
Basic methods and technological schemes for obtaining vegetable oils.....	113
A.Boimirzaev, Z.Kamolov	
Size-exclusion chromatography of some polysaccharide derivatives from natural sources.....	117
MECHANICS AND ENGINEERING	
U.Erkaboev, N.Sayidov	
Dependence of the two-dimensional combined density of states on the absorbing photon energy in GaAs/AlGaAs at quantizing magnetic field.....	124
I.Siddikov, A.Denmumaxamadiyev, S.A'zamov	
Investigation of electromagnetic current transformer performance characteristics for measuring and controlling the reactive power dissipation of a short-circuited rotor synchronous motor.....	136
Sh.Kudratov	
Evaluation and development of diagnostics of the crankshaft of diesel locomotives.....	141

Z.Khudoykulov, I.Rakhmatullaev	
A new key stream encryption algorithm and its cryptanalysis.....	146
T.Mominov, D.Yuldoshev	
Coordination of the movement of transport types in areas with high passenger flow.....	157
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev, S.Baxritdinov	
Analysis of research results according to international standards.....	163
R.Abdullayev, M.Azambayev	
Cotton fiber rating, innovation current developments, prospects for cooperation of farms and clusters.....	168
F.Dustova, S.Babadzhanov.	
Calculation of the load on the friction clutch of the sewing machine.....	174
Z.Vafayeva, J.Matyakubova, M.Mansurova	
Improvement of the design of the shuttle drum in the sewing machine.....	179
A.Obidov, M.Vokhidov	
Preparation of a new structure created for sorting of ginning seeds.....	185
Sh.Mamajanov	
Carrying out theoretical studies of the cotton regenerator.....	192
ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION	
A.Khojaev	
Methodological issues of organizing internal audits and control of off-budget funds in higher education institutions.....	199
I.Nosirov	
Theoretical foundations of establishing new technologies on personal management system.....	203
Z.Mamakhanova, D.Ormonova	
Specific characteristics of uzbek national art of embroidery.....	209
A.Raximov, M.Khusainov, M.Turgunpulatov, S.Khusainov, A.Gaybullayev	
Energy-saving modes of the heat treatment of concrete.....	213
ECONOMICAL SCIENCES	
M.Bekmirzayev, J.Xolikov	
Prospects for the development of service industries.....	222
A.Ilyosov	
Organizational and economic mechanisms to support the export of industrial products: a comparative analysis of foreign experience and proposals.....	227
I.Foziljonov	
The importance of multiplier indicators in assessing the effectiveness of the cash flow of the enterprise.....	232
K.Kurpayanidi	
Innovative activity of business entities in the conditions of transformation: a retrospective analysis.....	238

Sh.Muxitdinov	
Main characteristics of the risk management mechanism in manufacturing enterprises.....	248
Y.Najmiddinov	
Green economy and green growth. initial efforts of sustainable development in Uzbekistan.....	252
E.Narzullayev	
The methods for measuring the effectiveness of social entrepreneurship activity.....	259
E.Narzullayev	
Analysis of the management and development of environmental social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.....	265
F.Bayboboeva	
Legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity.....	270
Z.Boltaeva	
Foundations of neuromarketing strategy in industry.....	276
R.Rashidov	
Issues of regional development of small business.....	281
Sh.Abdumurotov	
Methodology for forecasting the competitiveness of an enterprise based on the Elliott wave principle.....	288
S.Goyipnazarov	
Assessment of impact of artificial intelligence on labor market and human capital.....	299
A.Norov	
Evolution of management science.....	307
K.Narzullayev	
Investment process in the republic of Uzbekistan.....	317
Kh.Irismatov	
Statistical analysis of assessment of the volume of the hidden economy in the republic of Uzbekistan.....	322
